

Prevalence of Work-Related Stress and its Associated Factors Among Textile Factory Employees

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Abstract:

This study was done to assess the prevalence of work-related stress (WRS) and its associated factors among textile factory employees in Western Tamil Nadu. A cross-sectional study was conducted from July 2023 to September 2023, involving 250 employees from four textile factories in Tiruppur district, India. Among the participants Sociodemographic details and stress levels were collected using a pre-tested, pre-validated and semi-structured questionnaire, which includes the Perceived Stress Scale-10 (PSS-10). The results showed that 68.4% of participants experienced moderate stress, 30% had low stress, and 1.6% reported high stress. No significant associations were found between gender, marital status, age, experience, or socio-economic class and stress levels ($p > 0.05$). But education level was significantly associated with stress, for the individuals with secondary education reporting higher stress ($p = 0.032$). The findings reveal the prevalence of moderate work-related stress among textile workers and suggest that educational background may be a factor in stress levels. Further research is needed to find additional factors contributing to WRS in this sector.

Key words:

Work-related stress (WRS), Textile factory employees, Perceived Stress Scale-10 (PSS-10)

Introduction:

The Indian textile industry is the second largest producer of textile garments and India is the 3rd largest exporter of Textiles & Apparel in the world[1]. India's textiles and clothing industry is one of the mainstays of the national economy[1]. The textiles and apparel industry contribute 2.3% to the country's GDP, 13% to industrial production and 12% to exports and the textile industry has around 45 million of workers employed in the sector, India has a share of 4.6% of the global trade in textiles and apparel[2]. The Indian textile industry continues to be the second largest employment generating sector in the country[2]. The World Health Organization (WHO) broadly defines work-related stress as the reaction people may have

when presented with work demands and pressures that are mismatched to their knowledge and abilities that challenges their ability to cope[3] . Stress occurs in a wide range of work circumstances but is often made worse when employees feel they have little support from supervisors and colleagues, as well as little control over work processes[4] . Work-related stress can be caused by poor work organization (the way we design jobs and work systems, and the way we manage them), by poor work design (for example, lack of control over work processes), poor management, unsatisfactory working conditions and lack of support from colleagues and supervisors. Leading management's focus on raising output and quality put a great deal of strain on staff, which in turn led to work-related stress. As a result, this issue has grown increasingly significant. The amount of stress and health issues that employees face are influenced by workplace features, as the research literature has repeatedly shown. Among these are mental health issues including anxiety, depression, and/or post-traumatic stress disorder, physical health issues, such as musculoskeletal disorders, and an elevated risk of physical illnesses or diseases, such as cardiovascular disease (with elevated blood pressure and muscle tension serving as precursors to physical health outcomes); social relationships, which can exacerbate a breakdown in relationships at work and at home[5] . Thus, stress at work impairs employees' performance (difficulty focusing and memory loss are examples of antecedents to poor work), increases the risk of work-related diseases and injuries, and ultimately has a negative effect on the organisation through lower output.

Although the impact and burden of WRS is huge, there is a limited study available in India regarding magnitude and associated factors of WRS among employees in the textile factories.

Therefore, the aim of this study is to assess the prevalence work related stress and associated factors of work-related stress among Textile employees in Western Tamil Nadu.

Objective:

- 1.To find the prevalence of work-related stress among textile factory employees of Western Tamil Nadu.
2. To find out the association of sociodemographic factors with work-related stress among textile factory employees of Western Tamil Nadu.

Materials and Methods:

Study setting and period:

A cross sectional study was conducted on textile factory employees of western Tamil Nadu from July 2023 - September 2023.

Study setting:

The study was conducted in Tiruppur district in 4 textile factories which is situated at western part of Tamil Nadu, India and it is one of the largest manufacturers of textile garments in the country. It contributed a 54.2 per cent of India's textile exports in FY22[6] .

Study Participants:

The study population consisted of all employees who were available at their place of employment during the study period and were included in the sample. The study included workers who had been employed by the textile factory for longer than six months before the

data was gathered. The study did not include any employees who were on yearly leave or severely ill at the time the data was collected.

Sample Size Determination and Sampling Procedure:

Early study by Habte belette et al(2020)[7] shown that prevalence of WRS among related textile workers is 45%. Presuming similar observation will be made in textile town of Tiruppur by allowing 14% relative error with 95% CI the calculated sample size was 250.

Universal sampling method was followed. All the participants of two different textile industries were included.

Data Collection Procedures and Tools:

After prior informed consent, pre validated semi structured questionnaire was administered to the employees by face-to-face interview. The questionnaire used here consists of two parts, part -A demographic details and part-B consists of pre validated Sheldon Cohen's Perceived stress scale-10(PSS-10) with Cronbach's alpha value of 0.754. In the PSS portion of the questionnaire, participants were to answer diverse questions of Likert-type scale (5 point), employed for every variable. The Points ranged 0 to 4, where 0 indicates no stress and 4 indicates high stress: 4-always, 3-often, 2- Sometimes, 1-Seldom, and 0-/Never, which substantiates on the prerequisites of the study. Individual scores on the PSS can range from 0 to 40 with higher scores indicating higher perceived stress. Scores ranging from 0-13 would be considered low stress. Scores ranging from 14-26 would be considered moderate stress. Scores ranging from 27-40 would be considered high perceived stress.

Statistical analysis:

The gathered data was cleaned and verified for accuracy before being entered into the computer. After that, the data were cleaned, coded, and imported into Microsoft excel and exported to SPSS for analysis.

Tables, texts, frequency, and summary measures were used to display descriptive statistics. For statistical test a two sided probability of $P < 0.05$ will be considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

A total of 250 participants from western part of Tamil Nadu were enrolled in the present study. Among the participants majority (74%) were male (Fig.no.1). The mean age of the population is 38.2 years. In this study most of the participants were moderately stressed about 68.4 percent, 30 percent were low stressed and 1.6 percent were suffering from high stress (Fig.no.2). Among the study participants most of them (70.8%) were married. While comparing Gender, Marital Status, Experience, Age, and Socio-economic class, with the stress level the p-values are greater than 0.05, indicating that there is no significant association between these variables and stress level (Table.no.1). For Education p-value ($p = 0.032$), suggesting a significant association between education level and stress level. There is compelling evidence ($p = 0.032$) to suggest that individuals with different levels of education experience varying levels of stress. Particularly, those with secondary education seem to report higher stress levels compared to other educational categories.

Discussion:

Prevalence of stress Level in Textile workers:

The prevalence of moderately stressed textile workers were about 68.4 percent. In a similar study, carried out by Sein et al, using Job Content Questionnaire, in April 2009, on 200 rubber glove factory employees in central Thailand revealed; prevalence of job stress was 27.5% and Low supervisor social support and high job insecurity were found to be associated factors[8,9]. The level of workers included only the labourers who worked in this textile industry. This may be the reason for high level of stress. Also, the difference in sample size and the study setting may be the reasons for this finding. Also, we have used Sheldon Cohen's Perceived stress scale-10(PSS-10) for assessing the study tool which differs with many of the other studies which contributes to the high level of moderate stress. Another study done by Belete et al[7] agrees with our findings with a prevalence of (45.2%).

Socio Demographic Variables:

Contrast to many textile industries majority of the workers were male about seventy four percentage. The textile industry was quite far from the city, considering the travel time it may have contributed for the same. The Mean age of the workers was 38 years, which signifies the main working population age.

Association of socio demographic variables with stress:

The socio demographical factors like Gender, Marital Status, Experience, Age, and Socio-economic class had no association with their stress level. This according to the authors was due to the selection of the study tool, sample size and study area. Moreover since the majority of the study population were from the upper and middle class, they may have a financial background of parental money or savings. Most of them were in the core earning age group and the authors speculate that they may an alternate source of income.

Strengths and Limitations:

Though the authors used a validated questionnaire to assess the stress level among the textile workers the study could not establish a clear temporal relationship between significantly associated factors and work-related stress.

Conclusion:

Though most of the textile workers had moderate amount of stress, there was no significant association between the socio demographic variables with stress component. More variables to consider in socio demography may help in finding association between the factors.

Fig.no:1 Gender wise distribution of study participants

Fig.no:2 Prevalence of stress among study population

Table.no.1

Comparison of socio-demographic variables with Stress level

VARIABLE		Stress level			P- value	Chi- square
		Low stress (75/250)	Moderate stress (171/250)	High stress (4/250)		
Gender	Male	60(80%)	120(70.1%)	4(100%)	0.132 NS	4.047
	Female	15(20%)	51(29.8%)	0(0%)		
Marital status	Married	50(66.6%)	125(73.1%)	2(50%)	0.387 NS	1.894
	Unmarried	25(24.4%)	46(26.9%)	2(50%)		
Experience	0-3 years	14(18.6%)	33(19.3%)	1(25%)	0.710-NS	3.753
	4-6 years	34(45.3%)	63(36.8%)	1(25%)		
	7-10 years	21(28%)	49(28.6%)	1(25%)		
	>10 years	6(8%)	26(15.2%)	1(25%)		
Age	18-24	6(8%)	14(8.2%)	1(25%)	0.588 NS	4.654
	25-34	32(42.7%)	74(43.2%)	1(25%)		
	35-44	15(20%)	33(19.2%)	2(50%)		
	>45	22(29.3%)	50(29.2%)	0(0%)		
Education	Illiterate	28(37.3%)	31(18.1%)	1(25%)	0.032	19.72
	Primary	5(6.7%)	7(4.1%)	0(0%)		
	Upper primary	3(4%)	16(9.3%)	0(0%)		
	Secondary	18(24%)	51(29.8%)	3(75%)		
	Senior secondary	9(12%)	40(23.3%)	0(0%)		
	Under graduate	12(16%)	26(15.2%)	0(0%)		
Socio-economic class	Lower middle class	13(17.3%)	27(15.7%)	0(0%)	0.858 NS	1.319
	Middle class	39(52%)	93(54.3%)	2(50%)		
	Upper middle class	23(30.7%)	51(29.8%)	2(50%)		

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